

1 **MAP3K10 is a therapeutic target in metastasis to the brain in lung cancer.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

4 East Islip, NY USA 11730

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 Central nervous system metastasis is a major public health problem, affecting a significant fraction of
7 humans with lung cancer, breast cancer and metastatic melanoma, among other solid tumors (1, 2).
8 Between 40-50% of humans with lung cancer will develop metastasis to the central nervous system
9 (CNS), where the primary tumor spreads to the brain or the other major CNS organ, the spinal cord (1, 2).
10 We performed expression screening by comparing total transcription in primary tumors and metastases to
11 the brain in humans with lung cancer to identify by quantitative methods kinases that promote survival of
12 tumor in the CNS (3). We identified the MEK kinase *MAP3K10* as a candidate therapeutic target in CNS
13 metastatic lung cancer. *MAP3K10* was differentially expressed and up-regulated in CNS metastatic lung
14 cancer. High expression of *MAP3K10* in the primary tumors of humans with lung cancer was correlated
15 with inferior first progression survival. Small molecule targeting of *MAP3K10* is a promising approach for
16 chemotherapeutic management of CNS metastasis in humans with lung cancer.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Achrol, A.S., Rennert, R.C., Anders, C., Soffiatti, R., Ahluwalia, M.S., Nayak, L., Peters, S., Arvold, N.D., Harsh, G.R., Steeg, P.S. and Chang, S.D., 2019. Brain metastases. *Nature Reviews Disease Primers*, 5(1), p.5.
2. Chamberlain, M.C., Baik, C.S., Gadi, V.K., Bhatia, S. and Chow, L.Q., 2017. Systemic therapy of brain metastases: non–small cell lung cancer, breast cancer, and melanoma. *Neuro-oncology*, 19(1), pp.i1-i24.
3. Memon, D., Schoenfeld, A.J., Ye, D., Fromm, G., Rizvi, H., Zhang, X., Keddar, M.R., Mathew, D., Yoo, K.J., Qiu, J. and Lihm, J., 2024. Clinical and molecular features of acquired resistance to immunotherapy in non-small cell lung cancer. *Cancer Cell*, 42(2), pp.209-224.